

AN EFFICIENT BUSINESS MODEL FOR AN ON-LINE MENTORING PLATFORM WITH ACTIVE INVOLVEMENT OF SENIORS IN THE CONTEXT OF THE POST-PANDEMIC REALITY

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Abstract

Purpose – Define an efficient business model for an on-line knowledge transfer platform between senior mentors and companies.

Methodology/approach – User needs analysis, market survey analysis, market demand, lean canvas and business model

Findings – the specific needs of each type of user must be fulfilled; for commercial success such a platform needs a unique selling point.

Research implications – co-creation workshops, mentors and companies surveys, user-based platform design, AI-based matchmaking tool.

Practical implications – the on-line platform sets up an environment where project based/specific information is transferred through individual meetings from senior experts towards young developing companies.

Originality/value – the on-line platform addressed the specific needs of engineering companies using an intelligent matchmaking tool to ensure that the best possible mentor is provided for a developing company.

Key words: on-line mentoring platform, intelligent matchmaking tool, business model.

Introduction

The current e-learning platforms – some of the most known are [udemy.com](https://www.udemy.com/), [linkedin.com](https://www.linkedin.com/), [coursera.org](https://www.coursera.org/) – offer self-learning standard content. The content is generally of a high quality, but it is not specific and customized, the interaction with the instructor is low, from here the lack of motivation of the student. This leads to a high abandonment rate. The fees for such training are relatively low and the service model is based on a high volume of sales for the same content. To be able to offer the same content to a large number of users, the content ends up being at a basic level. This represents a limitation for the users that would like to become experts in certain areas. In this way, the typical outcome for the end user is a certificate and not real knowledge or expert advice [Araka, et al 2020]. The e-learning platforms on the market have addressed in particular children, young and active people. From our research so far, there are no digital platforms whose main objective is the social involvement of senior people and which offers them the opportunity to become mentors, to give them the chance to transfer their knowledge to younger generations. [Gherman, et al 2021].

While the use of digital technologies increased in the last decade, they became, in many cases essential tools for many businesses in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic [Meyer et al. 2022]. Multiple businesses adopted on-line technologies mainly for communication purposes, and knowledge transfer platforms are one of the best practices in this regard.

The paper presents the development strategy and business model of an online platform for knowledge exchange developed in the framework of Ambient Assisted Living of the European Union, within an international partnership. The paper describes the Target groups and market, the go to market strategy, an overview of the WisdomOfAge platform, the Lean Canvas and Business model, developed to achieve successful commercial implementation.

Target Group & Market

The main target Group of the WisdomofAge platform will be made up of Industrial companies (Startups, SME) looking for a mentor to support the learning process of their employees. These companies will be mainly from European Union countries (platform will be developed in English, German, Romanian and French). The need for mentoring is high (figure 1) and the market is expected to grow by 20% per year in the next 5 years [Pisla et al, 2021]. WisdomofAge will focus on industrial companies, especially the Smart Manufacturing Sector.

Fig.1 - Analysis of the mentoring software market

Market Segmentation

The market will be made up of people and organizations that want to learn online and specialize with a mentor-based learning system. The market can be segmented in:

- a) Industrial companies (Startups, SME) looking for a mentor to support the learning process of their employees, and faster development of the company on specific fields/applications.
- b) Employees who want to specialize in other fields to advance in their career.
- c) Research organizations that need specific skills in related fields of activity.
- d) Young people aiming to improve their knowledge acquired in high schools or universities.
- e) Master and doctoral students who need practical experience in completing research.
- f) Start-up companies that need expertise in a certain field and need a mentor.
- g) Associations that want to support members through continuous training programs.

Go To Market Strategy

Digital Twin, as business partners, is responsible for Go to Market Strategies (figure 2). The company has a relevant experience in the market. It began as a start-up in 2016 and managed to grow the business to over 1 Million Euro in only 3 years by using effective marketing and sales strategies. The

company has strong marketing knowledge and a very good understanding of the need for industrial digital transformation. In 2019 the company was awarded by Siemens Digital Industries Software - Top Business Partner in Central Eastern Europe. Digital Twin has invested in the last 4 years in e-learning and has good experience in working online with instructors and students. Partnerships with professional associations represent an important aspect of the business plan; these agreements will (1) improve the awareness of the platform, (2) promote the benefits, and (3) attract early adopters. Also using these partnerships, will help us to get more feedback from the market and continuously optimize the business plan. WisdomOfAge (through Digital Twin) already signed partnership agreements to offer platform services and engage early adopters.

Fig.2 - Wisdom of Age Launch Go to Market Campaign Timeline for 2023

Product - Solution WisdomOfAge platform

WisdomOfAge is a business platform that takes advantage of the experience and background of people over 55 years old, enabling them to share their knowledge and solve specific problems for industrial companies. This collaboration includes on-line courses, training, projects management and other specific topics requested by companies. The platform end-users are grouped into two large categories: the seniors acting as mentors or teachers, and the industrial companies acting as beneficiaries or students. As WisdomOfAge solves problems of active industrial partners they ensure the sustainability of the platform which is free to use for all the senior mentors. WisdomOfAge is based on the concept of e-learning platforms` technology, extending it towards a creative and open environment where ideas are shared and issues are solved. The benefits for the senior mentors cover multiple areas: (1) financial support, (2) active ageing, (3) social integration, and (4) societal development through their experience. A challenge for the development of the platform is the creation of an intuitive and easy to use interface that will offer both mentors and students a pleasant experience in using the platform. By involving users from the initial stages of development and using the latest available technologies, the project team created a modern platform adapted to all types of users (figure 3).

Fig.3 - Correlation between Start-ups & SMBs problems, Elderly Mentors needs and the study conducted by the consortium

Added value versus competitors

Regarding the competition, all the platforms identified and analyzed by us are some general ones, especially Business to Consumer, and none of them offer a clear focus for the digital transformation of the industry and the transition to Industry 4.0. They are not dedicated to the elderly, they are not intuitive, they promote content at the beginner level. They also do not offer support services for the elderly, and do not present the benefits of mentoring as an effective form of learning or knowledge transfer. Wisdom of age comes with important competitive advantages over competitors, both in terms of included functionality, but especially in the way it better serves the needs of customers. Figure 4 represents a comparative table of these aspects and the positioning of the platform against competitors.

Fig. 4 - Competitors analysis and Positioning of the platform

Lean Canvas model

The user base for the WisdomOfAge platform consists of two separate groups (mentors and companies) which have specific needs and requirements which need to be assessed independently [Vaida, et al 2021]. In the early platform development these needs were studied through participatory design to correctly identify the specificity of each group [Riessenberger, et al 2022]. We used the Lean Canvas (table 1) to improve our business plan and to easily communicate with all the partners involved in the project during the development phase. This method offered us value orientations, focusing on what is important for success, a fast, clear and flexible approach.

Table 1. Lean Canvas Model for WisdomOfAge

Lean canvas object	Lean Canvas for Mentors	Lean Canvas for Companies
Customer Segment	Retired experts (tech, engineering and IT) Seniors who wish to work Older employees who want to work in additional projects	SMEs Start-ups
Early adopters	Adults (55+) Expertise in the field of technology (Automotive, Aerospace, Machinery), computer science, and engineering from Romania, Belgium, Switzerland.	Existing Digital Twin customers in Romania Members of Automotive Suppliers association Members of Factory 4.0 - Digital Innovation Hub
Problems	Desire to continue working even after retirement in the former field of work. Difficulties to stay active/ be socially engaged COVID-19 social restriction Increased retirement costs Experience of seniors vanishes from the labor market	Lack of specific experience, knowledge. The costs of an expert consulting. Difficult to find customized training/consultancy. Lack of networking (difficult to connect with experts). Difficulty to organize in person meetings with consultants due to the COVID-19 restrictions.
Existing Alternatives	Job platforms for seniors: Rent a Rentner (CH), Nestor (BE), Sixie (BE) Networking platforms: LinkedIn Timebanking Municipal organizations Self Employment (consulting basis)	
Revenue Streams	The platform is free for mentors.	Detailed revenue strategy is described in the Business Model.
Solution	WisdomOfAge Artificial Intelligence (AI) matchmaking Facilitates keeping work experience on the labor market A model that adapts to the time capacity of seniors (Flexible consulting) Facilitating social engagement Facilitating remote activities suitable for the post-pandemic reality	AI matchmaking tool using machine learning which matches the customers with mentors based on the skill desired and the level sought. Encompassing platform offering an end-to-end process from matching, and secure payment system. Available on demand.
Unique Value Proposition	Wisdom of Age creates a unique opportunity to age well in a digital world. Using artificial intelligence and user-friendly interfaces, it helps senior mentors to stay connected, be active, and share their valuable experience for the benefit of the younger people who now work in industrial companies.	Our AI based platform offers specialized and customized knowledge from experienced professionals to transform your business. Wisdom of Age gives you quick access to cost-effective networking.
Channels	Recruitment through existing networks (IAF, HA) Direct phone calls to existing contacts Presentations in organizations for the older adults Online marketing and advertising (Google Ads, AdRoll, Bing Ads, content marketing) Social media (articles) Events (conferences, fairs, conventions etc.) Through mentees (they can contact their former employees)	B2B approach with business partners in each market. direct phone calls to existing contacts 1-1 presentations online marketing and advertising (Google Ads, AdRoll, Bing Ads) Social media (articles) events (conferences, fairs, conventions etc.) through mentors and professional associations
Lean canvas object	Lean Canvas for Mentors	Lean Canvas for Companies
Key Metrics	Registrations on the platform Profiles of seniors on the platform Activities on the platform Matchmaking Time spent on the platform/frequency	Business performance: Conversion rate Number of customers Customer retention Number of leads Costs control

	Number of sessions / recurrent customers/business Churn rate / retention rate	Repeat purchase rate Product performance: AI Matchmaking accuracy Number of tickets/errors
Cost Structure	Labor costs (developers, marketing, administration, staff for sales force) Advertising costs, participation in events Hosting costs for platform Developing costs for algorithm → covered by labor costs Overheads (rent, loan, electricity bills etc.) Travel costs Costs for IT Software for research	Labor costs (developers, marketing, administration, staff for sales force) Advertising costs, participation in events hosting costs for platform developing costs for algorithm > covered by labor costs overheads (rent, loan, electricity bills etc.)
Unfair Advantage	Early engagement of older adults in the development process (End User-Testing) Consortium network (End Users Organizations) AI/ML Recommendation system to match mentors-mentees Guidance/accompaniment of the development of the platform by social scientists and tech Interdisciplinary / international exchange	Existing customers in Romania Consortium expertise in AI Digital Twin's team experience and skilled professionals End user organizations support Retired mentors from our customers

Business model

WisdomOfAge is a platform business model that creates value by facilitating exchanges between two or more interdependent groups. The category of service providers is represented by mentors with experience in the technical field who are more than 55 years old, and the other category we have clients (mentees) who can be start-up time companies, medium or large enterprises.

In order to make these exchanges happen, platforms harness and create large, scalable networks of users and resources that can be accessed on demand. Platforms create communities and markets with network effects that allow users to interact and transact. In the old model, scale was a result of investing in and growing a business's internal resources. But in a networked world, scale comes from cultivating an external network built on top of your business. This is the essence of how platform business models work.

Business use-case model

A start-up company is asked to optimize a manufacturing process. It is a unique opportunity to expand their business. The company has expertise in robotics, but they need external help with production planning. They do not have the time to develop necessary skills, nor the budget to hire a consultancy company. They only found general information on the internet. Approaching the WisdomOfAge platform, they follow the next three steps (figure 5):

Step1: An employee discovers the Wisdom of Age platform, creates an account and easily posts a request for a manufacturing mentor with extensive experience in production planning.

Step2: Our matchmaking platform quickly analyses all existing mentor profiles and recommends the most suitable mentors for the specific request of the start-up company.

Step3: Based on the suggestions, the company selects the best mentor and the mentoring journey begins.

The companies are able to successfully finalize new projects, while the mentors are glad to remain connected with the industry, share their valuable experience and increase their income for a better life.

Our platform reshapes the future of mentoring, supports senior professionals to remain active and age well in a digital world while democratizing access to knowledge for companies.

Fig. 5 – User Journey for Mentees

Pricing is one of the most essential elements of the business, and it plays a major role in determining whether the business will fail or succeed. In order to ensure that we have an intelligent and efficient pricing strategy, we have used several methodologies for a correct positioning of the services offered by WisdomOfAge on the market. Thus, in elaborating the prices for the matchmaking services offered by the platform, we analyzed information from 4 different categories:

1. Evaluate pricing potential, analysis of competitive prices
2. Willingness to Pay, studies with our end users to identify their preferences for purchasing our services.
3. Operating costs (maintenance, marketing and sales)
4. Revenue goals, brand positioning and target audience

For the first 6 months after launch, we will use the following pricing policy for services.

Basic: 250 Euro per mentor

Free mentoring request and fixed price for access to each mentor profile.

Project based pricing - this is an affordable way for customers to discover our solutions and benefits. The cost is low for a company, it will not be a barrier and there is a good chance that most customers satisfied with the services will upgrade to standard or pro options in the future.

Standard: 500 Euro per request

Fixed price for a mentoring request and free access to all suggested mentors for this request.

Value Based - this is based on what customers are willing to pay. According to our studies, this is the mode preferred by most potential customers. After the success of this pricing option, customers will upgrade to the Pro package and become loyal customers.

Pro: 1000 Euro per year

Subscription fee for unlimited service access.

Premium price - the price will be paid annually by the platform's clients and will allow them to send an unlimited number of mentoring requests and to access all mentors who will be recommended for each request.

Freemium Pricing - will be used for key partners of the platform to attract early adopters, to involve them in testing and to attract more customers. With access to their email inboxes, phone number.

Discussion and conclusions

The development of an efficient business model and commercial strategy is very often a deciding element for the success of the investment despite its performance. The marketing strategy for an on-line platform, WisdomOfAge, was presented. This platform addresses a well-known European challenge, namely an ageing population, which further leads to natural consequences: increasing retirement costs on the government side, an unexploited potential of knowledge and experience from the seniors on the industry side, and a feeling of uselessness on the seniors' side. WisdomOfAge provides also a competitive solution on the post-pandemic reality, considering the seniors represented the most endangered population segment of COVID-19. To ensure the marketing success, the platform development included the achievement of an AI based matchmaking tool that ensures the efficient pairing between the senior mentors and the engineering companies. As the two user groups have different needs independent surveys were conducted for mentors and companies, as illustrated in the Lean Canvas model. The business model targets the companies both as beneficiaries and payers to support the commercialization and market success. The European scalability must ensure the growth of all the involved actors to achieve a successful balance between supply and demand.

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